

IPBES nexus assessment

Chapter 6, data management report 1 – Nature-positive financial flows figure

Code: IPBES_NXS_6.1

Version: v2.0.0

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Description

This product is composed of two elements: 1) A data compilation that describes current estimates of the total annual volumes of biodiversity financing, how related this financing is to other nexus elements, and remaining biodiversity financing gaps. These data were sourced from a non-systematic literature review conducted within the scope of chapter 6 of the IPBES nexus assessment, and specific methodologies and sources for all estimates are documented in the raw datasets (BD_allFinanceFlows.csv). 2) A workflow and R-code scripts that produce figures that visualize these financial flows and their connection to other nexus elements that has been made available in a [Github repository](#).

Process overview

This product was produced in the following steps:

1. A non-systematic literature review was conducted by all chapter 6 authors.
2. Using this review, all estimated numbers regarding the following aspects of biodiversity financing found in the reviewed literature were compiled:
 - a. Estimates of the total annual volumes of public and private biodiversity financing (i.e., how much is currently spent on nature-positive activities) (e.g., from estimates of domestic taxes to private investments)
 - b. Estimates of the total annual volumes of biodiversity funding gaps (i.e., how much is needed for nature-positive activities currently, as well as in the future)
 - c. Other miscellaneous aspects of biodiversity financing such as the value of illicit biodiversity-related activities, the value of nature's contributions to people (NCP), or the valued risk of businesses dependent upon NCP.
3. For each estimated number identified, the methods used in generating this estimate were documented, including, wherever possible:
 - a. The direction of impact: whether the financial flow had nature-positive, nature-negative, or mixed impacts (alternatively, if it referred to financing gaps)

- b. The overall sector (public, private, or mixed funding sources)
 - c. The sector of economic activity related to the financial flow (e.g., agriculture, forests, fisheries).
 - d. The year the quantity of financing was normalized to: typically estimates of monetary values need to be deflated/normalized in order to be comparable across different years.
 - e. The certainty (if quantified, if mentioned whether it was under or overestimate)
 - f. The extent to which the financial flow impacted nexus elements: whether the methodology, the description, or documentation directly (or indirectly) indicated that a given financial flow also impacted any of the other nexus elements (water, food, health, climate).
4. [In progress] Data were cleaned and carefully selected to represent the most accurate and comparable numbers across estimates. Code was developed in order to visualize these different aspects of biodiversity finance (and the extent to which they are related to other nexus elements) and to present these figures in chapter 6. Further details on the selection and processing of data, as well as how they are used to create visualizations are available under the following Github repository: https://github.com/pacheco-andrea/finFlows_nexus

Protocol

The data were compiled from the existing, non-systematic literature review carried out by the chapter 6 team on the public and private financing of biodiversity (and biodiversity-related elements of the nexus).

- This yielded >150 observations from >25 unique sources including both grey literature and scientific publications.
- Data were last updated on 28.09.2023.

The analysis of these data is underway and more detailed steps in the cleaning, processing, and visualization of these data can be found at: https://github.com/pacheco-andrea/finFlows_nexus.

Files attached

The following files are available at https://github.com/pacheco-andrea/finFlows_nexus

ID	File name	File type	File size	Description
	BD_allFinanceFlows	.csv	46KB	Raw data compilation
	BD_financingGap	.csv	7KB	Raw data compilation
	/code BD_fin finFlow_Sankey	.R	20KB	Workflow and R scripts for producing figures